

Impact of socio-cultural background of students (secondary Schools) on learning English Language living in rural areas

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ABSTRACT: English has become an international language. In Pakistan it has become a compulsory subject of curriculum in schools. This study will be conducted to investigate the impact of socio-cultural background of students (secondary school) of rural areas of Multan in learning English as a foreign language. This research will be conducted to find out the impact of socio-cultural background in learning English as a second language at high schools, which are situated in the rural areas of Tehsil Multan, and refined the solution to minimize these problems. For this research population will be the students of high schools in rural areas/ villages of District Multan. In this research 50 students will be selected randomly as a sample from 10th class. A questionnaire will be used as a tool to collect the data about the impact of socio-cultural background of student, and the problem which are faced by the student in learning foreign language. In this study, the collected data will be analyzed in a statistically method to understand the problems of students in learning English language. This research will be conducted to find out the problem of students, it will assist teachers, and educational policy makers of Pakistan to overwhelmed all these difficulties which become hurdles for students in learning English living in rural areas.

Introduction

Today world has become a global village. Internet and social media remove all the distance and come closer to the whole world (Srinivasan 2018). All the people of these different communities share their ideas, suggestions and concepts by language. According to Lyytinen, People use language to express their emotions, feelings and coordination with each other. Infact English is the foreign Language. It is one of the most indispensable for communication (Ahmed 2011). After independence, English attains the official language status. The Governor of Pakistan Quaid e Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah enlighten the importance of English In first Educational Conference of Pakistan. He announced Urdu as a national language but also give the importance of English (Ahmed 2014). We can say that English language play a key role in global village. English is also known as a language of trade and commerce. English taught as a compulsory subject at different levels (Ahmed 2011). It is a second compulsory language in Pakistan. The skill of English spoken fluently create opportunities of success in life (Doliti & Mikanili 2011). Knowledge of English is spread in whole Pakistan but still the students of rural areas facing difficulties in learning and speaking of English. They do not have enough encouragement to learn and practice English (ponmozhi 2017). This research will analysis the impact of socio-cultural background of students of secondary School on English language learning living in rural areas of District Multan.

Impact of socio-cultural back ground of students in learning English Language

The socio-culture back ground has a great effect on the students in learning English language. There are various factors which create hurdles for the students in learning English language such as their culture, religion, bilingualism, illiteracy of their parents and family, lack of motivation, lack of resources and home environment (Alam, Ashikullah et al. 2018). In rural areas the villagers have more perfection in Islamic culture and values. They have strong attraction with Islamic values, they disagree with white people and take English as a second language, and the language of white people. Therefore, they are not ready to teach their children English Language. There are also some families which consider that our religion not permit to learn English. Illiterate parents do not encourage their children to learn English

language. The environment also effects the students they have to communicate in regional language with their community. So, they don't find the environment to practice or learn English, even in their schools English is taught only as a compulsory subject (Nunan 2003). In rural areas students use Urdu and regional languages in their schools. So, the students of rural areas with these family backgrounds are not motivated to learn English language.

Statement of Problem

Socio-cultural backgrounds of students have come to bear heavily on effective English use of most secondary students living in rural areas of district Multan. Consequently, there are various social and cultural reasons and factors that effect on the students in learning English language. This research will draw attention to such influences and elements affecting the learning, speaking and pronouncing the English as a foreign language. This research will examine that how the students are facing problems in learning English as a second language besides the interference and implication of their various mother tongues and regional languages during their academic course of secondary level in various schools situated in rural areas of District Multan (Zaman, Abbasi et al. 2025).

Objectives of study

These are some objectives of this research:

1. This research will explore which socio-cultural factors affect learning English language as a foreign language.
2. To identify how the socio-cultural background of the students living in rural areas, influence on his/her English language learning and competence.
3. To identify the problems and refined the solutions to minimize these problems.

Research Questions

1. What are the socio-cultural factors that affect the students learning in English language as a foreign language?
2. How does the socio-cultural background of students living in rural areas influence on their learning English as L2?

3. What are the main problems and how can we minimize these issues?

Significance of the study

This study will peruse the socio-cultural background aspects that influence effective English learning. This research will bring forth the external factors like family and cultural factors that impede English learning in non-urban areas. English is known as international language. Due to its international influence, it has been treated as special and influential language since bifurcation of the Sub continent and is an integral part of the syllabus.

This research will be conducted to investigate the impact of socio-cultural background of students in learning English Language of the secondary schools' students living in rural areas of District Multan. The findings of the study will help the English teachers to identify the socio-cultural factors that affect the students learning of English language at secondary level. This research will also provide comprehensive information for educational planners that how they will assist the students of rural areas to cope the situation. The findings of this study will provide direction and guidance in teaching of English at secondary level by motivating the students living in rural areas to learn second language.

Literature review

We are living in a poor and developing country Pakistan. Almost half of the inhabitants are residing in rural areas. They are mostly uneducated and ignorant. So, the socio-cultural background of students living in rural areas has a great effect in learning English as a foreign language.

Gudykunst & Kim in their research proposed that our cultures directly effect on our behavior. It influences through the norms and rules we use to guide our behavior when we talk and communicate with others in the society. Our cultural impact on our behaviors and discussions, it indirectly affects our daily basis discussions and speaking with individuals. In our society we are more conscious about our culture and we learn from our culture. learn when we are socialized into our cultures (Anyanwo,2016)

In rural areas people are unaware of the significance of English language. Saptawulan Hening Nariswariatmojo (2011 Surabaya, Indonesia) argued that in learning English language students have to face many problems. These problems are inside or outdoor factors. According to him family background, social relations and, social culture and social factors play a vital role in learning English as second language (Tariq,2013). Students living in rural areas have no educational background, their parents are uneducated. These students do not find comfortable environment to learn English. Even they are not allowed to use English words with the people surrounding them.

Many other researchers have worked on these issues. Narendra Rathod (November, 5, 2012 in an international conference on Global English) describes that social factors are really important to learn a foreign language. there is a connection between these social factors and the foreign language. Most of the studies show that the students having very low socio-economic background not successful in learning foreign language like the students who have very high socio-economic background. The socio-economics background of students really effects in acquisition of English as a foreign language. The students who belong very low socio-economic background are not provided with the facilities which can help them in learning English language. While on the other hand the students have higher socio-economic background are facilitated by their family to learn English language. (Tariq,2013)

The environment of student's home has also an influential role in learning English as a second language. M.S. Farooq, A.H. Chaudhry, M. Shafiq (Journal of Quality and Technology Management Volume 6) argued that the environment of the student's home effects on their educational performance. The students of the educated family have much better environment for academic success than the students whom parents are not educated. The students having illiterate parents do not find the opportunity to speak in English or to learn English from their parents an environment around them. If the students living in rural areas try to speak in English in their homes, they are insulted by the family they don't want to accept that their children use the language that they considered the language of English people.

Zafar Hayat Attari, Mohammad Arshad and Ehsan Elahi (Published: February 13, 2012 International Journal of Learning & Development ISSN 2164-4063 2012, Vol. 2, No. 1) discussed that socio-economic position effect the learning of their children (Jerrim, 2009) as they provide their children with educational resources. the form of providing educational resources. In this research the researcher again argued that socio-economic back ground of students has direct impact in learning English language as L2.

Many researchers work on the problems in learning English as a second/foreign language. There are also research on the socio-cultural factors which effects on learning English language as L2. According to Gardner and Lambert in learning of a second language motivation is an important element which encourages intercultural communication between communities of different cultural individuals (Dornyei, 2003). Motivation is the most important element of learning a second language. Christine Pearson Casanave in her journal (leaning a second language) argued that motivation is really important to learn a second language. If students have no motivation to learn second language the teachers should motivate them. They cannot learn a second language without motivation.

According to Gardner and Lambert integrative motivation is a positive attitude toward the second language learning in terms of strong likeliness for using this language for communication and adopting the culture of the speakers of that language (Gardner and Lambert, 1972). Gardner (1974) claimed in his early work that integrativeness is regarded as the psychological interest and likeness of a person to learn the other language in order to become closer to the culture of that second/foreign language. Students living in rural areas have lack of motivation. Their family do not motivate them to learn English language as they consider it a foreign language. So, lack of motivation really effects on students in learning English language as L2. Gardner's (2010) definition of integrativeness has been changed with the passage of time, to become the willingness for adapting certain features and characteristics of other cultural or language groups. This is not just a general likeness for the culture of the other language or second language rather a more effective likeness for a specific culture (Amin, 2019).

English language is an international language now a days. We cannot deny of its scope in all field of life.

English language getting official language status in Pakistan (Akram and Mahmood 2007). English language has proved its worth not only in Pakistan but all over the world. It became a symbol of modernism, that's why everyone adopt it and accept it as well.

English language is the source of communication within government sector, office's, banks and in educational institutes. In Pakistan context it become a symbol of success and respect (Rehman 2003; Masoor 2004). There are many backward areas where English is not being spread. English language is well known and spoken in Urban areas but not in rural areas. It is very sad moment for these rural area's darkness. Urban Areas discriminate of these rural area's population. Citizen of urban areas degrade the rural areas by their communication. English language is a scale of status and gain hegemony over the national and local language of Pakistan just like Urdu, Punjabi, Saraiki, Pushto etc. Due to all these aspects, it creates a fear of adjustment in population of Pakistan. This issue is also highlighted by many other researcher of countries due its sensitivity (Philipson 1992; Tonkin 2003).

Students living in rural areas have also face the problem of bilingualism. Their mother tongue and the local languages of their areas also have a great impact on their learning English as foreign language. In schools they learn English only as their compulsory subject. They do not take interest to learn this language.

Methodology

Quantitative research methodology will be used in this research by the researcher. According to Dornyei, "quantitative research involves data collection procedures that result primarily in numerical data which is then analyzed primarily by statistical methods." To find out the answer of their research questions, survey method will be used to collect the data from the schools of rural areas of District Multan.

For this research Population will be the students of 10th class district Multan living in rural areas.

I will select four secondary schools of rural areas of District Multan. Population of this study will be students of 10th class of these secondary schools. Sample of 50 students will be selected through simple random sampling. Table of random numbers will be used and these numbers will be assigned to the members of population. Number of tables will be according to the number of populations i.e. (the numbers from 000 to 099).

Research tool

For data collection questionnaire will be used as tool to collect the data from the nominated population to find out the impact of socio-cultural background of students in learning English language living in rural areas. Collect data will be based upon the questionnaire responses of the selected population from rural areas of District Multan. All the students will response voluntarily. The questionnaire will be framed with forty questions and these questions will be divided in seven variables: Family's background, Parents profession, Relatives, Parents education, Parents interest in learning ESL, Home environment and Religion. The questionnaire will be designed simply and in easy wordings so that it can be understood easily. The questionnaire will consist of close ended questions.

Data Analysis

According to the research statistical technique will be applied to analysis the data that will be collected from questionnaire.

Conclusion

The conclusion of this research will be drawn from the findings of data analysis.

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